

The Trend of Leaving Bangladesh: A Study on Emigration Intentions among Youth

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Date: June 3, 2026

Abstract: This study explores the emigration intentions of Bangladeshi youth, examining their opinions, current activities, and future goals. Primary data were collected through surveys and in-depth interviews with over 1,300 individuals aged 15–38 from both rural and urban areas between January 2024 and December 2025. Secondary data from BBS Labor Force Survey 2023-2024, BMET 2024 supported the findings and World Bank were used to validate the findings. Results indicate that a significant portion of youth intend to migrate abroad within the next 2–3 years, motivated by poverty, unemployment, limited opportunities, political instability, security concerns, corruption, and wage disparities. Their main objectives include financial stability, better career prospects, and international exposure. The study concludes that without strong anti-corruption measures, improved facilities, fair wages, mental health support, and protection of lives and property. The trend of emigration is likely to continue.

Keywords: Migration, Youth, Emigration, Bangladesh, Remittance

JEL Classification: J61, F22, O15, I31

Introduction: In recent years, Bangladesh has witnessed a notable increase in youth emigration. For many individuals aged 18–32, moving abroad has become a primary goal. Factors such as unemployment, wage disparities, limited access to higher education, and aspirations for a better standard of living drive this trend. While emigration contributes to remittance inflows, boosting the national economy, it raises concerns about skill shortages and brain drain. Understanding the perspectives of youth regarding their current activities and future aspirations is crucial. This study aims to provide firsthand insights to help policymakers design employment and education strategies that align with young people's aspirations.

Methodology: A mixed-methods approach was employed. Primary data were collected through surveys and in-depth interviews with 1,300 individuals aged 15-38 from rural and urban regions between January 2024 and December 2025. Purposive sampling ensured representation across different socioeconomic backgrounds. Ethical approval was obtained from Government Brajal College and informed consent was taken from all participants. Secondary data from the Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics Labor Force Survey 2023-2024, BMET 2024, and World Bank migration reports supported the findings.

Findings:

Note: Percentages do not sum to 100% as respondents could select multiple options.

Age 15–17: Approximately 23% of respondents were engaged in low-income occupations and reported disconnection from formal education, primarily due to economic constraints. A significant proportion expressed intentions to migrate to the Middle East, Europe, or other destinations. Some reported modifying age documentation to meet employment requirements abroad. Around 49% were enrolled in educational institutions in urban areas, 20% resided with relatives abroad, 10% reported no formal schooling and unemployment, and 5% indicated involvement in informal youth groups.

Age 18–30: Over 50% intended to pursue higher education in Europe. Approximately 15% had already migrated to Europe or the Middle East. Less than 20% aimed for government employment, while 3% aspired to medical professions. 70% were employed in the government, private, or agricultural sectors. About 3% reported experiencing severe mental distress and suicidal ideation. More than 5% reported engagement in informal or undocumented employment.

Age 31–38: Less than 10% reported unemployment. Forty-five percent were employed domestically, 20% were employed abroad, 7% reported involvement in informal economic activities, 3% held high-ranking positions, and over 15% were engaged in agriculture and fisheries. The intention to emigrate remained evident within this age group.

Reasons for Emigration:

Based on survey responses, the primary factors influencing emigration intentions among respondents include:

1. Political instability
2. Lack of personal and social security
3. Perceived corruption in public institutions
4. Inadequate public service facilities
5. Insufficient employment opportunities
6. Rapid population growth
7. Low wages and wage disparities
8. Perceived nepotism and lack of meritocracy
9. Uncertainty about future prospects
10. Dissatisfaction with existing governance and institutional systems
11. Weak educational infrastructure

Migration Statistics:

According to the Bureau of Manpower, Employment and Training (BMET), a total of 1,009,146 Bangladeshi workers migrated abroad for employment in 2024, marking a 27.4% decrease from 1,390,811 in 2023. Saudi Arabia remained the top destination, receiving approximately 627,000 workers, which accounted for 62.17% of total migration.

Source: Bureau of Manpower Employment and Training (BMET), 2024; Ami Probashi Annual Report 2024.

[1]

<https://en.prothomalo.com/bangladesh/v9h4atbie5>

[2]

<https://www.thedailystar.net/news/bangladesh/news/migration-drops-27pc-3817131>

- Overseas migration statistics of Bangladesh 2023-2025 (BMET, 2025)

Year	Emigration Rate	Comments
2023	1,390,811	Baseline year
2024	1,009,146	27.4% decrease from 2023
2025	1,130,757	12% increase from 2024

Note: The actual rate of emigration may be higher due to underreporting of illegal migration.

Source: Bureau of Manpower, Employment and Training (BMET), 2025.

- Fiscal Year Remittance Amount (Billion USD)

Fiscal year	Remittance Amount (Billion USD)	Source
2023-2024	\$23.9 Billion	Bangladesh Bank [1] https://www.bb.org.bd/en/index.php/publication/publicity/1/29
2024-2025	\$30.32 Billion	Bangladesh Bank [2] https://www.bb.org.bd/en/index.php/press_release/index

2025-2026	\$28.43 Billion	Bangladesh Bank [3] https://www.bb.org.bd/en/index.php/econdata/wageremittance Note: Data for FY 2025-26 is up to April 20, 2026, not full fiscal year.
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Recommendations:

1. Implement a zero-tolerance policy for corruption.
2. Establish a transparent, accountable, and patriotic government to ensure political stability.
3. Revise and improve existing rules and regulations.
4. Ensure adequate employment and fair wages.
5. Promote mental health and well-being.